

Local assets, local decisions and community resilience

The Challenge

Recently, Scotland has seen adverse weather-related disasters that have impacted rural life and business. In addition, rural communities have seen an increase in the proportion of older people and demographic shifts that may leave some rural communities in a disadvantage to long-term resilience. In order to best prepare for these pressures to short and long-term resilience, it is necessary to adequately measure and assess rural communities' resilience.

Policy Implication

Disaster and emergency preparedness do make rural communities more resilient. The Scottish Resilience Partnership helps to mitigate the negative impacts caused by emergencies and disasters. The Community Planning Partnerships help to mitigate threats to everyday resilience in rural communities. However, more needs to be done in terms of assessing a rural community's resilience to both emergency and everyday resilience.

Research

A panel – comprised of experts in resilience planning, academics studying resilience and representatives of the Scottish Government who help plan for resilience – was created to help identify key factors that should be included to assess how resilient a rural community is.

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Results

While emergency and disaster preparedness is critical, rural communities in Scotland should also be prepared to deal challenges such as the lack of connectivity, isolation and aging population. A Community Resilience Assessment Tool is being tested in rural communities in Scotland. This tool, which is bespoke to places in rural Scotland, will help these areas assess their own level of resilience and promote community engagement in the process of becoming more resilient.

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Funding

Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS)

Scottish Funding Council supported Universities Innovation Fund

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About

The Land Economy, Environment and Society (LEES) Research Group is one of the largest groupings of economists and social scientists working in the rural, agricultural and land based sectors in the UK. Our vision is to be recognised as one of the leading centres for agricultural and wider rural economic and social research globally, benefiting the land use sector, the environment and rural communities.

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